

INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract: As methodological and psychological-pedagogical studies show, the use of role-playing communicative games opens up wide opportunities for activating and optimizing the educational process, which is an important means of organizing pair and group work. The motivation for mastering a foreign language, first of all, is the professional need of a student who is preparing to become a highly qualified specialist with knowledge of a foreign language.

Keywords: the educational goal, skills, abilities, professional qualifications, speech etiquette, communicative competence, modern methodology.

Introduction

In the process of intercultural communication, a dialogue is needed not as the relationship of the cognizing subject to the cognized object, but as a relationship between different subjects entering into linguistic communication with each other about meaning. To intensify the educational process, the forms and means of training aimed at the active use of new methods of cognition in teaching began to be widely used. In the modern methodology of teaching foreign languages, interest in the theory of communication and methods of teaching communicative activity has increased. The idea is that all the material to be learned is presented in the form of steps towards achieving a common game goal. Thus, the entire course is a business game with a cross-cutting plot, divided into so-called "steps", each of which brings the trainees closer to the practical goal originally set for them.

In a modern university, a teacher of English for Special Purposes has to spend a lot of time developing teaching materials for a number of reasons. In some cases, this is due to the lack of English textbooks for students of rare specialties, in others - the high cost of educational materials, in the third - their unacceptability for educational purposes in general or for a specific educational situation. The development of training materials can take place on the basis of an already existing program or simultaneously with its creation.

Effective adaptation is about achieving consistency among several interrelated changes: teaching materials, methodology, students, course objectives, the language to be acquired and the context of its study, and the personality of the teacher and teaching style. This happens by changing some of the internal features of the textbook or teaching aid, dictated by the specific conditions in which the teacher has to work. At the same time, adaptation can relate to various components of the content of educational materials (exercises and assignments, texts, tests, etc.) and be qualitative and quantitative. It may be related to their need for personalization, individualization, localization and modernization .

Each person involved in labor activity performs a certain professional "role", for example, the head of the company, manager, secretary, tour guide, hotel administrator, restaurateur, etc. This suggests that when teaching a foreign language, a teacher should develop in students both the language skills of their narrow specialty and the skills of professional culture, taking into account the profile of a specialist. Professional communication is carried out only among people who have

general knowledge in a certain area, who own the conceptual and categorical apparatus of a certain field of activity and the corresponding system of terms. Business communication has its specific narrowly professional content, which is expressed by a certain "sub-language" with its characteristic terminological composition, certain types of texts, a special morphological and syntactic structure. So, the skills and abilities of business communication, as well as professional competence, are important components of the process of teaching professionally oriented foreign language communication.

Conclusion .

In the process of intercultural communication, a dialogue is needed not as the relationship of the cognizing subject to the cognized object, but as a relationship between different subjects entering into linguistic communication with each other about meaning. To intensify the educational process, the forms and means of training aimed at the active use of new methods of cognition in teaching began to be widely used. In the process of such work, students master the methodology of independent search for knowledge, and this is very important if we want not only to lay down knowledge, but also to arouse interest in learning a foreign language. One of the most effective ways to achieve your goals, in our opinion, is such a type of learning activity as reading. In the course of independent work with a foreign language text, the general and special horizons expand, and the creative thinking of students develops. Teachers of a foreign language face difficulties of a psychological and methodological nature at any stage of teaching a foreign language culture

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